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SJABLOON VALIDATIEPLAN NFI

Title

Validation of IC-ESI-MS method for the identification and quantification of low molecular weight cations related to pyrotechnics and inorganic explosives in casework samples.

Identificatie van het validatierapport	17CFS302 – Pyroprof project (MSCA no. 747249), 19/10/2018 Divisie Chemische & Fysische Sporen Team E&E
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1 Introduction

Until 2018 at the NFI's Explosive and Explosion Section, an analytical screening method (described in QOL00863) is applied to determine the ion (anions and cations) composition of aqueous extracts of casework samples related to inorganic explosives and pyrotechnic items (e.g. fireworks) [1]. This QOL00863 method is able to separate and detect 8 cations (i.e., lithium, sodium, potassium, ammonium, calcium, magnesium, strontium, and barium) and 8 anions within 45 minutes. The method for the analysis of cations is based on a chromatographic separation by an Ion Chromatography (IC) instrument coupled to a relatively non-specific detector [2]; a conductivity detector. The result of the current method gives a qualitative indication for the presence of the mentioned ions, because of its relatively low selectivity/specificity, in addition to quantitative information. Therefore, in order to improve the analytical methodology applied to this kind of samples, a new mass spectrometry (MS) detector with electrospray ionization (ESI) will be used, coupled to an IC as a complementary and more selective method for full identification and quantification of cations. This MS, a single quadrupole, is a more specific detector that allows to identify and quantify characteristic ion products with high precision and sensitivity [2]. Additionally, an on-line suppressed conductivity detector will be placed between the IC-instrument and the MS detector.

The IC-ESI-MS method will serve for the accurate and sensitive quantification of 22 low-mass cations in samples with a variety of matrices related to post-explosion forensic casework samples of pyrotechnic and inorganic explosives. The list of cations of interest (see **Table 1**) includes common low-weight cations (alkanes, alkane-earth, transition metals, post-transition metals, a lanthanide, and some inorganic and organic compounds) and selected organic compounds of interest that usually appear in or are related to this sort of casework. This validation plan for an in-house validation (single laboratory study) is set up in order to demonstrate if the performance characteristics of the IC-ESI-MS method are adequate for use for this particular purpose.

Table 1. The following cations of interest will be obtained from this list of salts or reagents.

Analytes	Formula	Obtained from
Lithium	Li ⁺	Lithium nitrate
Sodium	Na ⁺	Sodium chloride
Potassium	K ⁺	Potassium nitrate
Cesium	Cs ⁺	Cesium nitrate
Ammonium	NH ₄ ⁺	Ammonium nitrate
Ethylammonium	C ₂ H ₈ N ⁺	Ethylammonium chloride

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Urea	$\text{NH}_2\text{CONH}_2\text{N}^+$	Urea
Dicyandiamide	$\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{N}_4^+$	Dicyandiamide
Magnesium	Mg^{2+}	Magnesium nitrate hexahydrate
Calcium	Ca^{2+}	Calcium sulfate dihydrate
Strontium	Sr^{2+}	Strontium nitrate
Barium	Ba^{2+}	Barium nitrate
Manganese	Mn^{2+}	Manganese(II) sulfate monohydrate
Iron	Fe^{2+}	Iron(II) chloride
Cobalt	Co^{2+}	Cobalt(II) chloride
Nickel	Ni^{2+}	Nickel(II) chloride
Copper	Cu^{2+}	Copper(II) chloride
Zinc	Zn^{2+}	Zinc chloride
Cadmium	Cd^{2+}	Cadmium chloride hydrate
Aluminium	Al^{2+}	Aluminium sulfate hydrate
Lead	Pb^{2+}	Lead(II) chloride
Gadolinium	Gd^{3+}	Gadolinium (III) chloride hexahydrate

2 Methods and materials

- Reagents, standards, validation samples and real samples:

- Acetonitrile (ACN), isopropanol and methanol will be purchased from Biosolve BV (Valkenswaard, The Netherlands), ACN also from Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands), oxalic acid from Sigma-Aldrich (Schnelldorf, Germany). All reagents are of analytical grade ($\geq 98\%$), and they will be used throughout this validation process. Milli-Q grade water (ultrapure water) of $18.2 \text{ M}\Omega \text{ cm}^{-1}$ will be used for preparing mobile phases, measurement stock standards, reagents blanks and test samples, as well as for rinsing the autosampler system and for preparing the MS cleaning eluents.

- The 22 cations of interest will be obtained from their corresponding inorganic salt or chemical compound (see **Table 1**), obtained from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). From

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them, measurement individual stock standards/individual calibrators will be prepared at 1000 mg/L aqueous solution (i.e., in ultrapure water). In addition, based on these measurement individual stock standards/individual calibrators, reagent blanks/complex standard solutions containing all 22 cations will be prepared at several concentrations from 0.0002 µg/mL (or 0.2 ppb) to 30 µg/mL (or 30 ppm) (see section 4 for more information). Occasionally, individual reagent blanks/individual standard solutions could be prepared at indicated concentrations.

- Twelve matrices of interest in this type of casework will be used in the validation process as test samples: blood, rubber, metal, cotton, swab (alcohol pads 70% isopropyl alcohol, purchased from B. Braun Medical BV, Oss, The Netherlands), soil, plastic, cardboard, soot, rust, tile and tire.

- Analytical instrumentation:

- A Metrohm 919 IC Autosampler plus.

- A Metrohm 850 Professional IC equipped with a Metrosep C Supp 1 cation-exchange column (250 x 4.0 mm). The sample loop is 20 µL.

- A Metrohm IC Professional Conductivity detector.

- The eluent coming into the MS interphase will be split 70% to the waste and 30% to the MS (split mode). For that, two PEEK tubes (yellow PEEK of 70-80 cm with a diameter of 0,007 inch, directed to the waste and a red PEEK of 20 cm with a diameter of 0,005 inch coming into the MS) will be set in a T-piece.

- A Waters® SQ detector 2 instrument, equipped with a single quadrupole. The ion source is a Z-Spray ESI.

- Additionally, one of the high pressure pumps of a Waters® UPLC ACQUITY Binary Solvent Manager instrument will be use to implement an automatic post-column rinsing method for the MS interphase. This rinsing step will keep the MS interphase clean and safe from very low pH values, and it will be run by the end of a working day for 20 min.

- Analytical method:

- A mobile phase made up of 25% ACN in ultrapure water containing 4.9 mM oxalic acid.

- The IC will be used in isocratic mode at a constant flow of 1 mL/min and column temperature of 30°C. First, right after switching on the method, the eluent will be pumped with a high pressure pump at 0.8 mL/min during a minimum of 10 min. This step is required to equilibrate the system. Then, when the pressure is around 12.2 (or lower), the flow rate has to be increased up to 1 mL/min during a minimum of 5 min more. After this, the column will be equilibrated and ready to use.

- The isocratic separation method lasts 25 min. A re-equilibration step is not necessary between runs.

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- The MS instrument will be operated in positive (ESI+) mode. Specific masses in the range 18.00 to 250.00 m/z (see section 4 for more information) will be monitored by selected ion recording (SIR) mode, at different cone voltages. Five additional full scan channels (i.e., MS scan mode) at different cone voltages (i.e., 10 V, 30 V, 50 V, 70 V and 90 V) might be set in continuum for scanning the entire spectrum (18.00 to 400.00 m/z) looking for ions produced by unknown compounds in matrices (e.g., interferences). This MS scan mode will be used for casework when necessary. Other important conditions are: 1kV capillary voltage; 350°C desolvation temperature; 1200 L/Hr desolvation gas; 150°C source temperature.

- The MS interphase rinse eluent consist of 20% methanol in ultrapure water (v/v). This will be infused into the MS interphase at a flow rate of 0.45 mL/min during 10 min (running between runs when this method is combined with the method for the analysis of anions).

- Data acquisition

- All data acquisition will be performed using MagIC Net Professional version 3.1. software from Metrohm and MassLynx™ version 4.1. software from Waters. The applied methods are called: "cations – isocratic" in MagIC software, and "22 cation SIR" in MassLynx software.

3 Type of method

The type of analytical procedure to be validated is a **new qualitative and quantitative** method for the identification of low molecular weight cations present in samples related to inorganic explosive and pyrotechnic casework (e.g., water extracts obtained from pre- or post-explosion samples).

Chapter: Customer requirements

The results of the described method will typically be used to help relate samples from a crime scene to the use of (a particular type of) inorganic explosive material/mixture. In post-explosion cases small amounts of residues of the original explosive charge might be present in samples taken. In order to do this, the method must be able to detect and identify these residues in aqueous extracts of samples, at µg/mL levels (as present on/in the sample), in commonly encountered matrices. In order to deduce relationships between identified ions in the complex aqueous mixtures obtained, the quantification must be accurate within at least 10%. The level of identification certainty must be to accepted standards, or better [3-4].

4 Performance characteristics

The performance characteristics to be verified for the new qualitative and quantitative method will be:

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- Selectivity / specificity:

First, the retention time and the chromatographic resolution at the MS detector (baseline separation) of critical compounds, among the ions of interest (those included in **Table 1**) will be checked. Critical compounds are those that could be misidentified due to them sharing characteristics diagnostic ions when eluting at the same retention time (e.g., co-eluting). The theoretical diagnostic ions are collected in **Table 2**. Secondly, the ion fragmentation and ion-ratio of each compound of interest will be also studied after the analysis of a high concentration of each measurement stock standard/individual calibrator. The information obtained will serve to complete/correct the theoretical diagnostic ions and isotope abundances showed in **Table 2**. These experiments will also help to detect any additional false positive when using the ion products in the identification.

Thirdly, specificity/selectivity will be also verified by deliberately selecting and analyzing potential interfering substances (i.e., isomers, isobaric species, degradation products) that could lead to a false positive. For instance, the typical signals produced by the acetonitrile or oxalic acid will be checked. An example is the use of the isotope ⁴¹K or ⁴⁰Ca. The 41 m/z ion appears as a consequence of the eluent (background). They will be analyzed, and their retention times and main characteristic ions will be tested. Finally, relevant test samples (i.e., matrices) will be verified in order to identify additional potential interfering substances. Then, they will be fortified/spiked at a relevant and known concentration (this concentration depends on the range study's results) with the individual measurement standard/individual calibrators that have been stipulated as possible interfering substances with the identification and quantification of the target ions.

How to proceed:

- Some critical compounds have been identified. The resolution between cobalt and nickel, ammonium and urea, urea and lithium, and nickel and iron will be checked in order to ensure their identification by their diagnostic ions (**Table 2**).
- Then, high concentrated measurement standards/individual calibrators of each ion of interest (i.e., 100 µg/mL or ppm) will be analyzed in order to study the ion fragmentation and ion-ratio patterns.
- Potential interfering ions, if there are any, will be studied.

The effect of each detected interference over the region of interest, where the target analytes are expected to elute, will be investigated. In case of notable influence on quantification and/or false positive risk –this is, the impossibility of getting enough evidence of its identity with a minimum of identification points or in case of high chances of false-positive (i.e., $\alpha = 0.05$) [4]–, further method development will be implemented. In order to evaluate this: **(1)** the (relative) retention time will be taken into account as

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necessary criteria. For the purpose of assuring the correct measurement of time, the use of a stable system peak will be used. The (relative) retention time ratio should have a tolerance of $\pm 2.5\%$ [4], and the minimum acceptable retention time is twice the retention time corresponding to the void volume of the column [4]. And (2), the identification points will be taken from diagnostic ions (e.g., molecular ion, product ion), and isotope-abundance analysis of main stable isotopes (i.e., **ion-ratio study**) detected by the MS detector. The theoretical diagnostic ions and isotope-abundances of the compounds of interest have been collected in **Table 2** together with an estimation of total number of identification points for each compound. The mentioned experiments will help to fill in/correct the remaining information. In addition, the relative intensity of the diagnostic ions should be more than 10% in the reference spectrum and agree with the criteria mentioned in **Table 3**, which is a partial reproduction of the *table 4* of the following reference [4].

Table 2. Minimum number of identification points that can be earned by each analyte of interest based on their theoretical diagnostic ions and stable isotope-abundances.

Ion formula*	name,	(Relative) Retention Time	Precursor or molecular ion**	Main stable isotope ion and its ratio	Additional product ions	Minimum number of identification points
Lithium - Li ⁺	✓	89			66 131	3
Sodium - Na ⁺	✓	23			64	2
Potassium - K ⁺	✓	39.01				1
Cesium – Cs ⁺	✓	132.03			133.03	2
Ammonium - NH ₄ ⁺	✓	18				1
Ethylammonium - C ₂ H ₈ N ⁺	✓	46				1
Urea - NH ₂ CONH ₂ N ⁺	✓	61			18 44	3
Dicyandiamide - C ₂ H ₄ N ₄ ⁺	✓	85			68 126	3
Magnesium - Mg ²⁺	✓	195		²⁴ Mg ²⁵ Mg	24 95	6

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			²⁶ Mg	123	
			79/10/11%	236	
Calcium - Ca²⁺	✓	70	⁴⁰ Ca	79	4
			⁴⁴ Ca	88	
			97/2%		
Strontium - Sr²⁺	✓	105	⁸⁸ Sr	87	4
			⁸⁷ Sr	44	
			⁸⁶ Sr		
			82.58/7/10%		
Barium - Ba²⁺	✓	69	¹³⁸ Ba	89	4
			¹³⁷ Ba	155	
			¹³⁶ Ba		
			¹³⁵ Ba		
			71.6/11.2/7.8/6.5%		
Manganese - Mn²⁺	✓	226		71	4
				113	
				55	
Iron - Fe²⁺	?	73		114	3
				56	
Cobalt - Co²⁺	✓	59		141	2
Nickel - Ni²⁺	✓	58	⁵⁸ Ni	140	3
			⁶⁰ Ni		
			⁶² Ni		
			68/26.2/3.6%		
Copper - Cu²⁺	✓	63	⁶³ Cu		2
			⁶⁵ Cu		

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			69/30.8%		
Zinc - Zn²⁺	✓	194	⁶⁴ Zn	122	4
			⁶⁶ Zn	124	
			⁶⁸ Zn	126	
			48.6/27.9 /18.75 %		
Cadmium - Cd²⁺	✓	112	¹¹⁰ Cd	114	4
			¹¹¹ Cd		
			¹¹² Cd		
			¹¹⁴ Cd		
			¹¹⁶ Cd		
			12/12/24.13 /28.73/7.5 %		
Aluminium – Al²⁺	?	61		79	2
Lead - Pb²⁺	✓	208	²⁰⁸ Pb	223	4
			²⁰⁷ Pb	225	
			²⁰⁶ Pb		
			52.4/22/24		
Gadolinium – Gd³⁺	✓	176		172	4
				173	
				174	

* All ions are measured as +1.

** molecular ion (molecular weight of the cation form).

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Table 3. Maximum permitted tolerances for relative ion intensities using a range of Liquid Chromatography-MS technique. This table has been partially reproduced from [4].

Relative intensity (% of base peak)	LC-MS (relative)
> 50 %	± 20 %
> 20 % to 50 %	± 25 %
> 10 % to 20 %	± 30 %
≤ 10 %	± 50 %

- Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ):

The detection limits of this new method and this instrument (i.e., MS detector) will be measured for each analyte. The background noise of the detector during a single separation will be compared to the obtained signals (i.e., peaks) from test samples (i.e. swabs) and reagent blanks containing concentrations of the different analytes, close to or below the expected LODs [3]. The estimated instrument LODs for each analyte are shown in **Table 4**. The chosen measuring strategy is known as Signal-to-Noise (S/N) ratio, and it will be measured using the available tools offered in the above-mentioned MaxxLynx software. The following equation will be used:

$$\text{Signal-to-Noise} = \text{height of analyte} / \text{amplitude of noise}$$

MS signals will be considered as a peak for the LOD if it is 3 times higher than the noise of the detector [3], and for the LOQ if it is minimum 10 times higher than the noise of the detector [3]. The standard deviation have to be also calculated (S_0) [3].

How to proceed:

- Reagent blanks/complex standard solutions including each of the analytes of interest at relevant concentrations will be used for calculating the instrument LODs and LOQs. Those complex standards containing the 20 cations (all but *nickel* and *urea*, read next) will be prepared at concentrations x0.2, x0.5, x0.9, x1, x1.1, x2, where the lower expected LOD will be the reference (i.e., x1) (see **Table 4**). Each complex standard solution will be prepared 10 times, and analyzed 1 time for each solution.

- Overlapped ions with clear risk of suppression/ enhancement effect (*urea* and *nickel*) have to be studied separated, in individual standards in the same way and concentrations indicated above (at the beginning of this experiment, try first with x1, x0.9 and x1.1, then complete the dilution series if necessary).

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- In addition, test samples will be analyzed for obtaining the method LODs and LOQs. In this case, non-spiked swabs and spiked swabs with the reagent blanks will be measured. First, 10 non-spiked swabs will be extracted using the sample preparation protocol (i.e., NFI SOP 161501 [5]) and analyzed in triplicated. Second, three set of 10 swabs will be spiked with three relevant concentrations. One of those concentration have to be the estimated instrumental LOD (x1), and the other two should be concentrations above that LOD (x1.5 and x2). Each extracted sample will be analyzed one time.

Then, the minimum concentration at which the analyte of interest can be reliably detected and quantified by this instrument and method (i.e. with acceptable retention time, peak shape, mass spectral ion ratios; see below the rest of the performance characteristics) will be established.

Table 4. Expected instrument LODs for the analytes of interest at the MS detector, and their corresponding expected intervals including the expected LOQ (or the lower end of the working range) and the upper end of the working range.

Analytes	Expected LODs (µg/mL)	Expected interval (µg/mL)
Lithium	0.001	0.005 – 1
Sodium	0.001	0.008 – 8
Potassium	0.001	0.01 – 5
Cesium	0.001	0.008 – 20
Ammonium	0.05	0.1 – 8
Ethylammonium	0.005	0.008 – 2
Urea	0.005	0.008 – 10
Dicyandiamide	0.005	0.008 – 20
Magnesium	0.005	0.01 – 15
Calcium	0.001	0.03 – 20
Strontium	0.08	0.08 – 30
Barium	0.08	0.5 – 25
Manganese	0.005	0.05 – 20
Iron	0.08	0.3 – 30
Cobalt	0.005	0.01 – 30

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Nickel	0.08	0.1 – 25
Copper	0.03	0.5 – 25
Zinc	0.05	0.07 – 25
Cadmium	0.05	0.05 – 30
Aluminium	0.08	0.1 – 25
Lead	0.08	0.1 – 20
Gadolinium	0.08	0.1 – 25

- Method and instrument working ranges (interval), and linearity

The expected interval/range of interest spans from the LOQ of each analyte to upper end of the working range, i.e. those concentrations at which significant anomalies in the analytical sensitivity are observed [3], in this case to a maximum of around 30 µg/mL or ppm for some of the ions (see **Table 4**). There are two types of ranges that will be assessed: the method and the instrument working ranges. The method working range is related to the typical matrices of interest. The reason is that some interferences could cause non-linear responses.

How to proceed:

- In order to assess the instrument working range in the MS detector, complex standards at concentrations $\pm 20\%$ the lower (i.e., the LOD) and upper ends of the predicted working range of each ion of interest, besides 8 additional concentrations evenly spaced across that range, will be used. Each sample will be prepared 3 times. After the first round, the plotting of the obtained data will give a visual confirmation (i.e. a response curve) of the linear range (or dynamic or quadratic) and of the upper and lower limits of the instrument working range. Then, the other two rounds will be analyzed, and the regression statistics and residual plot will be studied in order to confirm the relationship between concentration and instrument response. Correlation coefficient should be of $R^2 \geq 0.995$. This proposed calibration procedure will be used for calibrating the instrument.

- Next, the method working range will be defined. This can be done using test samples (swabs) spiked at concentrations $\pm 20\%$ the lower and upper end concentrations of the range of interest, besides 6 additional concentrations evenly spaced across that range, will be used. Each sample will be prepared 3 times. They will be extracted using the sample preparation protocol (i.e., NFI SOP 161501 [5]) and analyzed one time. The plotting of the obtained data will give a visual confirmation (i.e. a response curve) of the linear range (or dynamic or quadratic) and of the upper and lower limits of the method working range.

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Alternatively, the data obtained from the bias and precision studies (see below) can be used for the evaluation and/or support of the method working range study.

- Quality of the results: bias/recovery (or “finite” trueness), and precision

This section describes the quality of results obtained [3]. It expresses the closeness of a single obtained result to a true value. It will be determined studying two performance characteristics: recovery or bias, which is also known as “finite” trueness, and precision (or accuracy).

How to proceed:

- Firstly, bias/recovery will be studied through a recovery experiment, spiking test samples (i.e., the above mentioned matrices) with reagent blank at 3 different concentrations (low, medium and high), in replicates of 8 [6]. Low concentrations shall be approximately 3 times the lowest end of the working range of the method. High concentrations shall be within approximately 80% of the highest end of the working range of the method. Medium concentrations shall be near the midpoint of the low and high concentrations. Then, they will be extracted and measured, and compared with the results of un-spiked blank matrices. The relative spike recovery R' (%) will be calculated from the difference between the mean value of compound concentration obtained from spiked samples and the mean value from un-spiked samples, and divided by the added concentration (fortification level). As this term is a percentage, that value have to be multiplied by 100 [3]. This value should be within 80-120%:

$\% = [\text{mean value spiked test samples} - \text{mean value un-spiked test samples} / \text{fortification level}] \times 100$

If there are co-eluting compounds from matrices, and those compounds affect to the target ions (ion suppression or enhancement effects; the so-called matrix effect), then those effects will be studied.

- In addition, possible ion suppression or ion enhancement effect at the MS detector will be studied on those semi- and overlapped ions, for instance nickel, urea, lithium and dicyandiamide; ethylammonium, magnesium and manganese; zinc, gadolinium and cobalt; and copper and aluminium. This experiment will consist in analyze fixed concentration of one of the overlapped compounds together with the other overlapped compounds present in the same sample at variable concentration (e.g., nickel/lithium at concentrations w/w 1:0.1, 1:0.5 or 1:0.9). The relative recovery values (%) will be compared in order to assess possible ion suppression or enhancement effects.

- Precision is a measure of how close results are to one another [3]. Two measures of precision will be assessed:

- (1) Repeatability (within run precision and between run precision), specifically retention time and peak area repeatability.
- (2) Intermediate precision (ruggedness) will be also assessed.

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This study will be carried out as a single experiment following the instructions given in reference [3], applying one-way analysis of variation (ANOVA) [6-8]. Two analysts will prepare and analyze 6 reagent blanks each day during 5 days in a row at 3 different concentrations (low, medium and high). The first week of analysis each one of them will prepare and analyze every day the 6 reagent blanks at medium concentration. They will use different equipment (pipettes, flasks, etc.). The following two weeks, the analysts will analyze the samples at low and high concentrations. The mean, and the standard deviation or relative standard deviation (SD or RSD) will be assessed [6], and one-way ANOVA will be applied [7, 8]. Those coefficient of variation values for retention time should be within $\leq 5\%$ for each compound, and within $\leq 20\%$ for peak area. This equation should be applied:

$$\text{Coefficient of variation (\%)} = [\text{SD} / \text{mean}] \times 100$$

This experiment is also valid for the **ruggedness/robustness study** (see below).

- Ruggedness / robustness

This characteristic tries to identify the variables (e.g., analytical parameters, conditions or nominal values) which have the most significant effect over qualitative and/or quantitative aspects when performing the method [3]. The close control of those variables will ensure its correct performance.

How to proceed:

The experiment for evaluating this characteristic will be based on the Plackett-Burman experimental design [8-10], using test samples of interest, 8 real factor and 3 dummy variables as is explained in [10] (see **Table 5** and **Table 6**):

- As the mobile phase composition is critical in this kind of analytical method, the influence of some variations in its composition will be assessed:

1) the influence of variations in mobile phase composition over peak area, retention time and asymmetry will be assessed. Several mobile phases made with different concentrations of ACN and oxalic acid will be made and then, the analytical results will be compared and, if necessary, a significance test will be carried out [9, 10].

2) the influence of using different suppliers (this is different brands) of the main mobile phase compounds will be assessed. Several mobile phases made with different brands of ACN will be applied to the analysis of some test samples of interest, then the results compared, and, if necessary, a significance test will be carried out.

- Column temperature influence will be also assessed. Different column temperature will be set during three consecutive runs in order to study its influence on the retention time, peak area and asymmetry.

- Mobile phase flow rate influence will be studied on the retention time and peak area of the analytes of interest. Flow rates at 0.8 and 1 mL/min will be assessed.

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- The chromatographic column equilibration step will be also assessed since a non-efficient equilibration of the column might affect to the run, for instance, with high back-pressure issues or with no stability in the baseline. Several equilibration times (5, 10 and 20 min) will be tested. The obtained retention times and peak areas will be compared.

- The ion source conditions (i.e., contamination issues) will be studied. A MS interphase (post-column) rinsing method will be implemented in this method to avoid contamination and loses of sensitivity. During the validation process, the efficiency of this cleaning method will be assessed. The system will be run with and without using the MS cleaning method.

- Isopropanol is present in the most common matrix, i.e., swab. Therefore, its presence in a sample solvent (Milli-Q water) will be tested. The average amount of isopropanol in a swab is 0.5 mL. A higher amount of isopropanol (double volume) will be added to a sample, or no isopropanol will be included in order to evaluate its effect.

Performance results (retention, separation and quantification) of the 12 experiments (**Table 6**, from A to L), repeated 3 times each, will be compared to each other and evaluated. Additionally, the **intermediate precision** mentioned above will be also part of this study (i.e., influence of several analysts and measurements along several days).

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Table 5. Analytical parameters to be evaluated and the normal and variation conditions.

Parameter	Upper value (+)	Nominal value (0)	Lower value (-)
Solvent concentration in mobile phase	27% ACN	25% ACN	23% ACN
Salt concentration in mobile phase	5.1 mM Oxalic acid	4.9 mM Oxalic acid	4.7 mM Oxalic acid
Solvent supplier	Biosolve	Biosolve	Sigma-Aldrich
Column temperature	35 °C	30 °C	25 °C
Flow rate	1 mL/min	1 mL/min	0.8 mL/min
Column Equilibration time	20 min	10 min	5 min
MS source contamination	Using MS cleaning method	Using MS cleaning method	No MS cleaning method
Isopropanol in the sample	Higher amount of isopropanol than usual	Isopropanol coming from the swabs (average amount)	No isopropanol
Dummy 1	+1	0	-1
Dummy 2	+1	0	-1
Dummy 3	+1	0	-1

Table 6. Factorial combinations of the analytical parameters for the study of robustness by Plackett-Burman experimental design [9].

Parameter	Combinations											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Solvent concentration in mobile phase	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
Salt concentration in mobile phase	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-
Solvent supplier	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	-
Column temperature	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	+	-	+
Dummy 1	+	-	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	-
Column Equilibration time	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+
Dummy 2	+	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	+
Isopropanol in the sample	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	+	+
Flow rate	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	-
MS source contamination	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-
Dummy 3	+	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+
RESULTS	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L

- Stability and carry over

Stability of the individual calibrators in water solution and reagent blank/complex standard solution during storage will be assessed. This study might be used as part of the bias study. Additionally, another carry-over study for the autosampler instrument will be carried out.

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How to proceed:

- The solutions will be stored for several days/weeks (i.e., 48 hours, and one to four weeks) in the dark at different temperatures (i.e. -20, 4, and 20 °C). Half of the solutions stored at 20 °C will be also kept under natural light (next to a window), and the other half over the bench or in the fume extractor. First, the complex reagent blank will be study at 0.9 ppm. Then, if necessary, the individual calibrators will be studied. The results will be given in % of analyte remaining, taken as 100% the analytes analyzed from the freshly prepared solution. The maximum degradation accepted will be 80% remaining. This experiment could be stopped at any time if we observe significant changes.

- The carry-over effect will be studied in a Milli-Q blank sample after inject a sample with the highest calibrator concentration (30 µg/mL). The obtained signal should not exceed 10% of signal of lowest calibrator.

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5 Tijdpad

Activity	Performance by	Planned end date
Validatie plan opstellen (inclusief aanmaken labjournaalbladen, afstemming met betrokkenen) en accordering	Mattijs Koeberg	23-October-2018
Inventarisatie veiligheidsrisico's (PBM aanschaffen, instructies etc)		October-2018
Vastleggen afspraken leverancier t.a.v. prestatiekenmerken, validatiegegevens leverancier, onderhoud(scontract), aanspreekpunt leverancier, reactietijd bij problemen, inwerken mdw'ers etc.	Jacinta Jansen	October - 2018
Logboek apparatuur aanmaken (apparaat markeren nog niet gevalideerd en kalibratiestatus)	Chris-Jan Kuijpers	October - 2018
Gebruiksaanwijzingen, CD's etc. archiveren	Chris-Jan Kuijpers	October - 2018
Onderzoeksmateriaal verzamelen	Chris-Jan Kuijpers and Carlos Martin Alberca	October - 2018
Uitvoeren validatieonderzoek	Shanaya Soeknandan Leonie Uittenbogaart	Third week of October 2018 on
Registratie van de locatie van het monstermateriaal (ruimte X of vernietigd)	Jacinta Jansen	
Opstellen documentatiemap (alle communicatie vastleggen, o.a. tussen afdelingen etc.)	Jacinta Jansen	
Back up regelen (bv ICT)	Jacinta Jansen and I.T.	October - 2018
Opstellen validatierapport	Carlos Martin Alberca	November - 2018
Accordering validatierapport	Mattijs Koeberg	December - 2018
Opstellen implementatieplan	Carlos Martin Alberca	July 2019
Uitvoeren interne check en evt. constatering en verhelpen	Carlos Martin Alberca	July 2019
Specifiek extra item voor validatie software etc	??	??

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Communicatie met RVA

Mattijs Koeberg

August-
2019

6 Autorisatie

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